

Policy Brief

The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource: Shared capacity and equitable access for the benefit of One Ocean, One Health

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Executive Summary

This policy brief highlights the strategic importance of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource within the interconnected frameworks of One Ocean and One Health, recognising that ocean ecosystem health, climate regulation, biodiversity, and human wellbeing are deeply interdependent. Marine microorganisms underpin global biogeochemical cycles, support marine food webs and fisheries, and provide vast genetic diversity with major potential for innovation in biotechnology, healthcare, environmental remediation, aquaculture, and climate mitigation. As such, the Ocean microbiome represents both a critical scientific frontier and a major socio-economic opportunity.

The brief emphasises that Digital Sequence Information (DSI) derived from marine genetic resources circulates globally, creating governance challenges for existing Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) frameworks under the CBD and the emerging BBNJ Agreement. Because the ocean spans Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), and because DSI can move independently of physical samples, ensuring transparency, traceability, and equitable benefit-sharing is complex. Jurisdictional fragmentation, incomplete metadata standards, and limited interoperability across databases further complicate monitoring and reporting.

Analysis of international sequence databases reveals significant geographic imbalances: the majority of Ocean microbiome samples originate from the Northern Hemisphere and from EEZs, while access to these resources is overwhelmingly dominated by countries in the Global North. These disparities highlight capacity gaps between regions and reinforce concerns about equity in the digital age.

The brief calls for strengthened monitoring and reporting protocols for DSI, including mandatory and harmonised metadata standards, coordinated integration of access metrics across major data platforms, and improved interoperability among diverse data repositories. It further supports governance approaches that balance open science with fair and equitable benefit-sharing, alongside targeted capacity-building to ensure broader global participation. By aligning science, policy, and equity, the Ocean microbiome genetic resource can be governed in a way that advances sustainable development, strengthens the blue economy, and delivers on the principles of One Ocean, One Health.

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One Ocean, One Health

The One Ocean concept recognises that the world's Ocean is a single, interconnected system that transcends national boundaries and links ecosystems, climates, and human societies. It emphasises that activities in one region – such as plastic pollution, overfishing, or carbon emission – can have far-reaching impacts across the entire Ocean. By promoting integrated, cooperative governance and sustainable use of marine resources, the One Ocean approach encourages countries to work together to protect biodiversity and maintain ecosystem services for present and future generations. The One Ocean concept is characterised by the highly dynamic nature of the seascape compared to landscape. The seascape is shaped by physical processes such as large river plumes, circular and horizontal currents that cross the globe, as well as vertical currents driven by coastal winds and water density. This highly dynamic system is home to the Ocean microbiome, microscopic organisms such as viruses, bacteria, archaea, phytoplankton and zooplankton that drift with currents. As a result, the Ocean microbiome is highly connected across the globe.

The One Health concept recognises that the health of humans, other lifeforms, and ecosystems are closely linked and interdependent. It emphasises that many global challenges – such as emerging infectious diseases, antimicrobial resistance, food safety, and environmental degradation – cannot be effectively addressed in isolation. By encouraging collaboration across disciplines, One Health promotes innovative and coordinated solutions. Decades of research on the human microbiome – microorganisms associated with specific organs – has led to a better understanding of an individual's health as a whole, and to the detection and mitigation of specific diseases. Following the same holistic approach, there is growing evidence that the Ocean microbiome can be used to diagnose marine ecosystem health and assess capacity to support ecosystem services. The development of anti-microbial resistance by microorganisms in coastal waters is one example of the close connection between the Ocean microbiome and human health. Decades of research on plankton have revealed the importance of the Ocean microbiome in regulating the Earth's climate and responding to anthropogenic carbon emissions, and in supporting marine food webs and fisheries.

Figure 1. One Ocean, One Health. LEFT: The human microbiome is diagnostic of human health. MIDDLE: The Ocean microbiome is diagnostic of Ocean health. RIGHT: The One Ocean concept relies on the highly dynamic nature of the seascape compared to landscape, leading to high connectivity of the Ocean microbiome.

2.1 Scientific Importance

Fundamental research on the Ocean microbiome is essential to better understand:

- ☀ **The fabric of marine ecosystems:** The ocean microbiome underpins marine food webs by driving primary production (e.g., photosynthetic microbes) and nutrient recycling, forming the biological base that supports all higher marine life.
- ☀ **Evolution and biodiversity:** The ocean microbiome represents one of the largest reservoirs of genetic diversity on the planet. Studying its genes reveals evolutionary innovations, novel metabolic pathways, and previously unknown branches of the tree of life.
- ☀ **Global biogeochemical cycles:** Marine microorganisms regulate major Earth systems by mediating the cycling of carbon, nitrogen, sulfur, and phosphorus. Their genetic pathways control processes such as carbon sequestration and nitrogen fixation, which are central to climate regulation.
- ☀ **Ecosystem stressors and drivers of change:** Microbial community structure and gene expression respond rapidly to environmental change, making the ocean microbiome a sensitive indicator of ocean warming, acidification, and deoxygenation, while also influencing climate feedback mechanisms.
- ☀ **Discovering underexplored environments:** Metagenomic research on marine microbes uncovers new enzymes, biochemical processes, and survival strategies (e.g., adaptation to extreme pressure, temperature, and salinity), expanding fundamental scientific understanding of life under extreme and variable conditions.

2.2 Socio-Economic potential

The Ocean microbiome genetic resources hold significant potential for economic development and innovation across multiple sectors:

- Biodiscovery and healthcare:** The ocean microbiome contains vast, untapped genetic material that lead to the development of medicines, including cancer treatments, antibiotics, and anti-inflammatory drugs.
- Environmental remediation:** Microorganisms from the ocean microbiome are used in bioremediation to clean up oil spills, heavy metals, and other pollutants. This capability supports industries focused on environmental cleanup, reducing costs and enhancing sustainability efforts.
- Aquaculture Innovation:** Combined with aquaculture feed, microbial strains from the marine environment help promote growth, boost fish immunity and reduce disease outbreaks, leading to lower treatment costs and higher productivity.
- Industrial applications:** The enzymes and proteins derived from ocean microorganisms are used in various industries, such as waste processing, biofuels production, and plastics degradation, offering more efficient and sustainable production methods while driving economic growth.
- Climate change mitigation:** Ocean microbes play a crucial role in carbon cycling and the regulation of greenhouse gases. By harnessing these microbes, we can develop technologies for carbon sequestration, helping mitigate climate change impacts while creating new economic opportunities in green technologies.

2.3 Policy Impacts

Investment in research and innovation related to the Ocean microbiome helps:

- Achieve healthy and productive oceans (UNSDG14)** through better and more accurate monitoring and management of marine ecosystems.
- Avoid significant adverse impacts**, including those of climate change through better assessments and forecast of marine ecosystem vulnerabilities.
- Develop ecosystem services** to ensure the long-term sustainable management of marine resources.
- Increase EU leadership and competitiveness** in the blue economy by developing new technologies and new value chains.
- Improve the professional skills and competences** needed for a rapidly changing blue economy.

The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource

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Marine Genetic Resources (MGRs) refer to any biological materials of marine origin, including the functional units of heredity (DNA & RNA) as well as their expression into the structural units of life such as proteins, metabolites and whole organisms. The Ocean Microbiome genetic resource refers more specifically to MGRs from marine microorganisms, including viruses, bacteria, archaea, phytoplankton, and zooplankton. **Digital Sequence Information (DSI)** refers broadly to any data derived from genetic resources. In the case of the Ocean microbiome, DSI generally results from the sequencing, mass spectrometry and imaging of whole organisms, genes, proteins and metabolites. The Ocean microbiome genetic resource holds significant scientific, ecological, and economic value, supporting climate regulation, food webs, biotechnology, and healthcare innovation. Because the Ocean microbiome is highly interconnected across national boundaries, the governance and use of this genetic resource raise important transboundary and equity considerations.

Figure 2. The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource. Digital Sequence Information resulting from the sequencing, spectrometry and imaging of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource – including whole organisms, genes, proteins and metabolites – supports humanity in areas such as food security, climate regulation and healthcare.

3.1 Shared Capacity and Equitable Access

Digital Sequence Information (DSI) derived from the Ocean microbiome genetic resource may originate from samples collected in:

- **Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ)** – EEZs are maritimes zones extending up to 200 nautical miles (370 km) from a coastal state's shoreline. In this zone, the coastal state has sovereign rights over natural resources (both living and non-living) in the water column, seabed, and subsoil. This includes rights to explore, exploit, conserve, and manage marine resources, as well as jurisdiction over activities such as marine research and environmental protection.
- **Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ)** – ABNJs are parts of the Ocean that lie outside any national jurisdiction. These areas are typically located beyond the 200 nautical miles of an EEZ, and they encompass the high seas and the deep seabed (the area known as the Area, under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, UNCLOS). In ABNJs, no single nation has sovereignty, and the resources are considered to be part of the common heritage of mankind, managed under international frameworks. Key governance mechanisms in ABNJs include treaties such as the BBNJ Agreement and the United Nations.

Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) was developed under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol. It set the foundation for shared capacity, equity and international coordination. Since then, the definition of DSI and the establishment of the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) agreement have posed some challenges:

- 1 DSI challenges the ABS paradigm:** ABS was designed around the management of physical access to tangible genetic material. DSI bypasses these control points because users may utilise sequence data without conventional access-agreements, thus creating gaps in governance.
- 2 Gaps between international frameworks:** Both the CBD and the BBNJ Agreement now recognise DSI, yet institutional mechanisms, monitoring tools, and legal clarity are still evolving and incomplete.
- 3 Jurisdictional fragmentation:** Differences between EEZs (national jurisdiction) and ABNJ (shared governance) complicate regulation, traceability, and equitable benefit-sharing.
- 4 Lack of transparency and traceability:** Mandatory metadata standards, interoperable clearing-houses, and reporting protocols are critically needed to track DSI provenance and usage.

A number of governance mechanisms and policy approaches are under discussion to address these challenges. Each has its own set of advantages and drawbacks, reflecting the complexities of managing data, ensuring fair benefit-sharing, and balancing open science with equity.

- 1 Multilateral fund for DSI benefit-sharing** encourages global collaboration and preserves open access to scientific data. It simplifies the implementation of benefit-sharing by pooling resources from various stakeholders. On the other hand, weak traceability of where and how DSI is used can complicate monitoring and enforcing benefit-sharing. It is also complex to implement effectively at a large scale.
- 2 Jurisdictional Differentiation (EEZ vs ABNJ)** recognises and respects national sovereignty over marine resources within Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) while maintaining international cooperation for Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ). On the other hand, this dual system (different governance for EEZs and ABNJs) can create administrative challenges and increase the complexity of governance across different regions.
- 3 Database integration and metadata tagging** helps improve the transparency of DSI use by linking data to its original source, making it easier to track the flow of genetic resources and ensure that benefits are shared fairly. On the other hand, the tagging DSI can slow down the process of data sharing and introduce technical costs, which could make database integration more difficult to manage.
- 4 Capacity-building and non-monetary benefit-sharing** promotes equity and participation, particularly in developing coastal states, by providing resources and support to build local research capacity and technological infrastructure. On the other hand, this approach lacks direct financial returns, which may make it less appealing for some stakeholders focused on immediate economic benefits.

3.2 The Geopolitical Context

The Earth's surface can be divided between sovereign nations on land, Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) in coastal waters, and Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJs) in the high seas. Together the EEZs and ABNJs cover 71% of the surface of the globe, and – with an average depth of 3,700 metres – provide over a billion cubic kilometers of habitat for the Ocean microbiome. This genetic resource represents a huge potential for scientific, innovation and economic growth. Marine Genetic Resources (MGRs) collected within EEZs fall under national sovereignty, while those collected within ABNJs are governed by international frameworks. Once converted into Digital Sequence Information (DSI), however, data originating from MGRs can circulate globally without clear jurisdictional anchors, complicating distinctions between sovereign rights and shared governance. The geographic distribution of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource between EEZs and ABNJs and between the Northern and Southern Hemispheres is therefore relevant when discussing shared capacity and equitable access to that resource. The high seas (ABNJs) cover approximately 50% of the planet's surface compared to only 21% for EEZs. This contrast is more pronounced in the Southern Hemisphere with a greater proportion of high seas (66%) compared to EEZs (12%), whereas it is less pronounced in the Northern Hemisphere with similar proportions of EEZs (28%) and high seas (38%).

The One Ocean, One Health concept fundamentally cuts across the geographic divisions or boundaries of sovereign nations on land, Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJs). However, differences in the scientific, economic and political interests of sovereign nations, combined with contrasting capacity to exploit the Ocean microbiome genetic resource, challenge the One Ocean, One Health concept. The governance mechanisms outlined in the previous above aim to balance the One Ocean, One Health approach with national interests, ensuring that both scientific advancement and equitable distribution of benefits are considered.

Figure 3. Geographic coverage of Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and Land masses. It is important to note that joint regimes (e.g. waters bordering Antarctica) and overlapping claims are included in the statistics shown here for the EEZs. **LEFT:** The Southern Hemisphere is dominated by the ABNJ (66%) compared to the Northern Hemisphere where the ABNJ, EEZs and Land masses cover nearly equal shares. **CENTRE:** Globally, the ABNJ covers half (50%) of the planet. **RIGHT:** Global map showing the distribution of ABNJ, EEZs and Land masses in the Southern and Northern Hemispheres.

3.3 Monitoring and Reporting protocols regarding Digital Sequence Information (DSI)

Monitoring and Reporting protocols are essential to track the provenance, use and flow of DSI derived from the Ocean microbiome genetic resources and other biological resources. These protocols aim to ensure transparency, accountability, and compliance with international frameworks like the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol. They require that standard metadata, such as the origin and context of samples, are embedded in digital data repositories. By implementing consistent tracking systems, these protocols help monitor the utilization of DSI, ensuring that benefits are shared equitably with resource-providing countries, while also safeguarding the integrity of open science. Although progress is being made in developing and implementing Monitoring and Reporting protocols for DSI, significant work remains to harmonize global standards, enhance transparency, and ensure equitable benefit-sharing in the digital age.

With the aim to highlight challenges around monitoring and reporting on DSI, we attempted to provide metrics about the provenance and access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources. Statistics were obtained from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), one of three sequence data archives of

the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) where scientists deposit and access DSI as well as metadata of the associated genetic resources. The three data archives (ENA in Europe, GenBank in the USA, and DDBJ in Japan) mirror their data and metadata, so that **provenance statistics** obtained from one of the three archives reflect the entire INSDC database. On the other hand, **accession statistics** obtained from one of the three archives reflect only the accesses made through that archive. The number of accessions presented here therefore underestimates the total number of accesses from the INSDC by perhaps two-thirds, and the statistics regarding the origin of accessed records or the origin of users accessing records reflect only the user community of the European Nucleotides Archive, which may differ from that of GenBank in the USA, and DDBJ in Japan. Additionally, only access to sample metadata are considered here rather than access to the DSI themselves (sequences and their annotations), which is ultimately a more meaningful metric and would likely be some orders of magnitude greater than the number of accesses shown here.

As of January 2025, the INSDC counted over 46 million sample records, 2 million of which were identified as Marine Genetic Resources (MGRs). Our analysis of available provenance metadata – including geolocation, sampling depth, taxonomy and sequencing strategy – indicated that a quarter of those samples (0.5 million) targeted the Ocean microbiome genetic resource, but only 0.3 million had geolocation. At that date, these records were accessed nearly 0.8 million times via ENA metadata queries alone.

Provenance of Ocean microbiome genetic resources

Figure 4. Provenance of Digital Sequence Information (DSI) from Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). It is important to note that joint regimes (e.g. waters bordering Antarctica) and overlapping claims are included in the statistics shown here for the EEZs. **LEFT:** The vast majority of DSI (83%) originates from the Northern Hemisphere. In both Hemispheres, the vast majority of DSI originates from EEZs (90% in the North & 87% in the South) compared to the ABNJ. **CENTRE:** Globally, DSI originates predominantly from EEZs (90%) compared to the ABNJ. **RIGHT:** Global map showing from which Countries' EEZs the DSI originate, with greatest numbers (darker green shades) from the EEZs of the United States of America, China, Australia, Canada and Japan. (data obtained from ENA <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295>)

Overall, **access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources reflects their availability.** When comparing the two hemispheres, the vast majority of samples (83%) originate from the Northern Hemisphere (Figure 4), which is reflected in the number of accesses (82%) from the Northern Hemisphere (Figure 5). When comparing marine jurisdiction areas (EEZs and ABNJs), samples originate predominantly from EEZs (90%) compared to the ABNJ (Figure 4), which is also reflected in the number of accesses (84%) from EEZs (Figure 5). In other words, communities interested in Ocean

resources tend to exploit all available resources rather than regional subsets. This may result from growing interest in addressing global questions, and greater capacity to exploit large data bases using machine learning and Earth system models. Globally, **Ocean microbiome genetic resources are collected overwhelmingly in the Northern Hemisphere (83%), highlighting an important geographic gap.** Despite equivalent areas covered by marine waters (ABNJs + EEZs) in the Southern and Northern Hemispheres (78% vs. 66% respectively; Figure 3), less than 20% of Ocean microbiome genetic resources originate from the Southern Hemisphere (Figure 4). In both Hemispheres, **Ocean microbiome genetic resources are collected overwhelmingly in EEZs (87-90%)** rather than ABNJ, and statistics show that samples originating from EEZs were collected in greater numbers in the national waters of the United States of America, China, Australia, Canada and Japan (Figure 4). Not surprisingly, this reflects greater ease with which research is conducted in coastal EEZs, and more generally, the concentration of developed countries with high income economies in the Northern Hemisphere. From a scientific and economic point of view, there is a strong interest in filling this gap and collecting Ocean microbiome genetic resources from the underexplored ABNJs, particularly in the Southern Hemisphere. Policy agreements and diplomatic initiatives such as the All Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance contribute to fill this gap.

Access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources

Figure 5. Access to Digital Sequence Information (DSI) from Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). It is important to note that joint regimes (e.g. waters bordering Antarctica) and overlapping claims are included in the statistics shown here for the EEZs. LEFT: The vast majority of accesses (82%) target DSI from the Northern Hemisphere. In both Hemispheres, the vast majority of accesses targeted DSI from EEZs (88% in the North & 68% in the South) compared to ABNJ. CENTRE: Globally, the vast majority of accesses target DSI from EEZs (84%) compared to ABNJ. RIGHT: Global map showing which Countries access DSI, with greatest numbers (darker green shades) by Germany, Italy, the United States of America, China and the United Kingdom. (data obtained from ENA <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295>)

Adding to the fact that Ocean microbiome genetic resources largely originate from the Northern Hemisphere, our results clearly show **that countries from the Northern Hemisphere overwhelmingly dominate (99%) the number of access, and the exploitation of genetic resources**, irrespectively of the latitude at which these were collected (Figure 6). This of course reinforces ongoing debates about equity, capacity, and fair benefit-sharing in the digital age. On the other hand, the fact that Ocean microbiome genetic resources are accessed in greater numbers by users located in Germany, Italy, the United States of America, China and the United Kingdom (Figure 5) may simply reflect ENA's user community, and such statistics would likely differ if access via other INSDC archives are considered.

Figure 6. Number of accesses to Digital Sequence Information (DSI) by countries from the Northern and Southern Hemispheres, broken down by latitude of the accessed DSI. All latitudes confounded, the vast majority of accesses (99%) are by Countries from the Northern Hemisphere (LEFT, blue) compared to accesses (1%) by Countries from the Southern Hemisphere (RIGHT, orange). (data obtained from ENA <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295>)

3.4 Recommendations

Policymakers and international organisations are considering several actions to ensure equitable, transparent, and effective governance of marine digital sequence information (DSI). These are outlined in this policy brief and we support them fully. With the aim to highlight challenges around monitoring and reporting on DSI, we attempted to provide metrics about the provenance and access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources. These are our recommendations:

Metadata about the origin and context of samples are often incomplete – If monitoring and reporting protocols aim at providing metrics about the provenance of DSI, governance protocols from the CBD and BBNJ should enforce the adoption and usage of existing and perhaps more prescriptive metadata standards such as those developed by the Genomics Standards Consortium (GSC).

There are multiple platforms and entry points to access DSI – If monitoring and reporting protocols aim at providing metrics about access to DSI, a coordinated approach is needed in order to harvest and integrate access metrics from multiple DSI access points, including at minimum the INSDC archives, the various genomics analysis platforms such as MGnify, and data aggregators such as OBIS and GBIF.

DSI generated from marine genetic resources include many data types – Digital Sequence Information may be obtained from the sequencing, spectrometry and imaging of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource, which data are archived in various domain-specific data bases. If the aim is to provide metrics about the full breath of DSI, policy actions will be needed to support the development of data interoperability across domains.

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